

COMMENTS ON SESSION 604: CREATING AN INTEGRATED SYSTEM OF DATA AND STATISTICS ON HOUSEHOLD INCOME, CONSUMPTION AND WEALTH

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Abstract

In 2024, the Committee on National Statistics at the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine released a report recommending that the federal statistical system take steps to produce integrated data on income, consumption, and wealth. These data, the report argued, were essential to guiding policymakers in addressing the Nation's most serious economic and social problems. The recommendations asked federal statistical agencies to expend considerable resources to realize this important goal and included specific milestones for making progress over a 5-year period

One year later, session 604 at the 2025 Joint Statistical Meetings (JSM) in Nashville, TN offered an overview of the recommendations, reviewed progress made over the past year and looked realistically at the capacity of the federal statistical system for implementing the proposed changes given recent cuts in staffing and budgets. While some progress has been made, especially at the U.S. Census Bureau, in the current budget environment, to make progress will require significant effort from the academic and non-profit communities. Fortunately, these groups are already making important contributions and, with proper support from the agencies, could provide much needed leadership and resources to help create a more integrated system of data on income, consumption, and wealth.

Key Words: Income, Wealth, Consumption

1. Introduction

The consensus report, *Creating an Integrated System of Data and Statistics on Household Income, Consumption, and Wealth: Time to Build*, was issued by the Committee on National Statistics (CNSTAT) at the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine in summer 2024.ⁱ Through it, the committee seeks to address shortcomings in currently available data on these three important aspects of individual well-being. While there are existing data on each of these topics, they are produced by different federal agencies with little or no coordination, resulting in conflicting and sometimes confusing estimates. The report provides a set of recommendations, that would result in integrated data on income, consumption, and wealth, created using harmonized concepts, and methodologies. The report also seeks to improve timeliness, quality, and coverage of data as well. The goal is to produce trusted data about who has how much and from what sources. Such data would help to guide development and evaluation of government policies and enable analysts to better estimate the impacts of economic shocks.

This report was authored by a distinguished panel of mostly economists, with deep expertise in studying changes in the distributions of wealth, income, and consumption and what those changes mean for the health of a society. The recommendations mainly focus the necessary characteristics of new integrated data that tell a consistent, interpretable story about the well-being of U.S.

¹ The opinions expressed in this paper are the author's alone and do not necessarily reflect those of the Tax Policy Center or the Urban Institute.

citizens. Each of the chapters provide specifics on how concepts should be defined, the data requirements, and potential methods for integrating existing or newly devised data series. Figure 1 illustrates two proposed approaches that select a single data source to serve as the foundation or base of the ICW and then add information from other data sources in a piece-wise fashion to create a final dataset.

Figure 1: Potential ICW Frameworks Recommended in The CNSTAT Report

The CNSTAT report is aimed primarily at the federal statistical system. While the U.S. has a decentralized statistical system, the Chief Statistician of the United States, through policies, regulations, and leadership of the 26-member Interagency Committee on Statistical Policy (ICSP), provides some centralized coordination. One theme of the report is the need for closer coordination and collaboration among those agencies whose data the committee identified as useful for measuring income, consumption, and/or wealth. The report includes recommendations for strengthening the chief statistician’s leadership role in encouraging and overseeing this collaboration. The report also calls for an advisory panel made up of users to ensure the resultant ICW data meet a wide range of needs.

The goals of the eponymous Topic Contributed Session at the 2025 Joint Statistical Meeting were to publicize the recommendations to a broad group of stakeholders, report on the progress that has been made in support of the recommendations, and suggest aspects of the report that may require additional thought, especially in light of current existential challenges faced by the federal statistical system.

2. The Statistical System Has Changed Since the Report was Issued

The CNSTAT report includes 16 recommendations and assigns nearly all the responsibility, and therefore cost, of implementing the recommendations to a handful of federal statistical agencies and units – the Census Bureau, Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA), Statistics of Income at IRS (SOI), Federal Reserve Board (FRB) and Social Security Administration (SSA). For example, Recommendation 3.2 asks the agencies to collaborate on a report detailing how each defines variables, like income, that are fundamental to ICW, in order to create a baseline

to start addressing definitional differences in constructing new ICW data. However, some of these differences reflect specifics of the core missions of each agency. For example, the definition of income used by SOI is determined by tax law and differs from that used by BEA for the National Accounts. It is important to recognize that while developing consistent definitions is essential for some economic studies, there are also important uses for data produced using legacy definitions. This means that in some cases realizing the report goals will require agencies to produce two different sets of data, rather than simply improving existing products.

The report was initially drafted in early 2024, and the panel no doubt assumed stable or slight increases in annual funding over the 5-year workplan included in the report. Unfortunately, in early 2025, the budget outlook for these agencies, and indeed the whole statistical system, changed in ways the committee could not have envisioned. One principal federal statistical agency, the National Center for Education Statistics, has been effectively eliminated. Every agency has faced steep declines in resources, some more than others, and there have been a number of leadership changes across the system. These headwinds have required several agencies to postpone or cancel planned surveys and new products, and in general, resource and other constraints will make it challenging for the agencies to continue producing statutorily required products for release on traditional timelines, much less take on new work.

In fairness, even when the report was issued in August 2024, the budget outlook for some agencies was not great. For example, BEA was already reducing staff, restricting travel and training opportunities for staff, eliminating lower demand core products, and ending long-term contracts for acquiring key external datasets. Given these challenges, it was disappointing that nearly all the report recommendations ask the agencies to do more – produce new linked data and develop methods for harmonizing concepts and methodologies, produce and release detailed new tables, and implement new privacy preserving technologies to support increased data sharing and researcher access. However, the report didn't suggest new revenue streams to help fund all the new stuff. Failure to account for the resources that would be required to implement the CNSTAT recommendations, and omitting strategies for meeting this need, are the most disappointing aspects of the report.

Thus, if federal statistical agencies were to try to implement the report recommendations on their own, it would require both a refocusing of agency priorities and introduction of new products that will almost certainly exceed already decreased budgets and put important legacy products and their users at risk. Fortunately, the papers in this session make clear that the agencies do not have to do this important work on their own. The academic and non-profit communities are already making important contributions to creating ICW and, given the current environment, they will need to play substantial roles in the future. For example, external researchers could produce the report noted above using publicly available documentation and their own past experience working with data produced by the agencies. Likewise, part of Recommendation 5.4 suggests using statistical data already in the public domain to produce a proof of concept ICW to help guide future agency-led efforts. Because the data are already public, this could and should be done by researchers outside government to demonstrate the value of these data to decision-makers. Most important, it will be essential for potential external users of ICW to work together to build support and advocate for dedicated resources to enable the transformational work the report envisions if substantial and sustainable progress is to be made.

2.1. Overcoming Growing Privacy Concerns is an Import Challenge

A challenge to data producers that will impact the future of ICW data is the public's growing concerns over the safety of sharing personal data, which has contributed to sharp declines in survey response rates over time. Americans have also been wary of allowing the government to amass personal data, even when there are strong privacy protections. Amy O'Hara's paper lays out an appropriate framework for protecting the privacy of data providers whose data are used to construct ICW data.ⁱⁱ This framework envisions tiers of access to ensure that a researcher gets just the minimum information needed to address an approved project. Some analyses would be supported using privacy preserving technologies that would allow statistics to be computed without actually

co-locating the data. O'Hara has been a leader in developing and evangelizing these methods, working at all levels of government to learn how privacy preserving technologies can be implemented to address specific needs. But, gaining acceptance of these tools will require significant external support to build capacity for leveraging them among data providers and data users, whose technical capabilities vary greatly.

While the tiered access framework and application of privacy preserving technologies align with best practices for protecting confidential data, these may not adequately address the concerns of data providers, including survey respondents, given recent high-profile and unprecedented uses of data for enforcement purposes, such the use of IRS and other federal data to support Department of Homeland Security immigration enforcement activities.ⁱⁱⁱ These data providers may be not be convinced that the data collected for statistical purposes will be safeguarded from inappropriate uses. It is essential then to engage with the data privacy and data user communities to better understand evolving privacy concerns and tolerances. Specifically, feedback is needed to understand whether both the planned methods for protecting data and the language used to describe these protections resonates with the data-providing public. If not, the statistical system must be willing to adapt its approach to protecting data based on findings. It is likely that more education will be required to overcome anxiety and misinformation among some data providers, and that some planned uses of data may need to be scaled back. Likewise, data users will need encouragement to embrace new, more restricted data access modes, and new statistical tools must be developed to make these tiers practicable. Organizations, like American Statistical Association (ASA), Association of Public Data Users and the Data Foundation seem uniquely placed to help lead efforts to better understand public perceptions, assist with educational efforts, and support innovation.

3. Despite Challenges, Progress is Being Made

Despite the headwinds, the presentations by Bruce Meyer and David Johnson highlight significant progress toward developing new statistics compatible with those recommended by the CNSTAT report.^{iv, v} Bruce Meyer and his co-authors have brought together data from a range of administrative and survey data to build and refine the Comprehensive Income Database (CID). Using the data sets shown in Figure 2 for 2014-2016, they apply a combination of rules-based adjustments, substitutions, and item imputation to create 'blended' data, drawing on the strengths of each source. This is thoughtful, painstaking work that results in data that better align with national macro estimates than estimates based on either survey or administrative data alone. Using these data, their paper demonstrates the considerable benefits to policy-makers and evaluators from consistent income and consumption data.

David Johnson highlights the Census Bureau's National Experimental Wellbeing Statistics (NEWS), a project that takes Meyers approach to the next level by drawing on the broader range of income and poverty data available to the Bureau. As illustrated in Figure 3, this approach draws on 2016-2021 data from even more sources than CID to correct errors in contributing data sources, fill in missing values, and adjust for various sorts of bias to a create comprehensive measure of income.^{vi} Census states that they are producing these data in a transparent, reproducible, evidence-based manner, using input from stakeholders. They note that the sources of bias and error vary from year to year and they have developed methods for customizing their integration process that are both timely and adaptable.

The approaches used by both NEWS and CID align with CNSTAT recommended approach for building ICW data and represent important steps forward. However, using rules-based approaches for database construction, that is, creating datasets by choosing values from various sources to add missing details and correct for errors, should be just a starting point, not an end. This is because these methods often require choosing among different values for similar variables across multiple datasets to create a version of information that is closer to the "truth." This may result in better data as compared to any single source, but it would be nice to better understand the model of respondent behavior that these practices are trying to correct. For administrative tax data, a

Figure 2: Data Sources Used by The Comprehensive Income Database

Administrative Data Sources

Income Source	Administrative Source	Income Unit	Income Frequency	States Covered
Earnings	W-2 (IRS), Form 1040 (IRS)	Individual & Tax Unit	Annual	All
AGI & Other Income	Form 1040 (IRS)	Tax Unit	Annual	All
Retirement Income	Form 1099-R (IRS)	Individual	Annual	All
Social Security	PHUS & MBR (SSA)	Individual	Monthly	All
SSI	SSR (SSA)	Individual	Monthly	All
Veterans' Benefits	US VETS Data	Individual	Annual	All
Taxes (simulated)	Form 1040 (IRS)	Tax Unit	Annual	All
SNAP	State Agencies	Household	Monthly	20+ States
Housing Assistance	PIC & TRACS (HUD)	Household	Monthly	All

Figure 3: Data Used by The Census NEWS Project

foundational source for both projects, it is clear that taxpayers have incentives to minimize their reported income in some circumstances. However, lower income taxpayers tend to have relatively straight-forward finances that are subject to a high degree of third-party reporting, which reduces

opportunities for error (under-reporting) by this group of taxpayers. For lower income taxpayers with business income, which is often not subject to third-party reporting, research by Raj Chetty and John Friedman found significant bunching of income for those who were trying to maximize claims of the Earned Income Tax Credit (EITC).^{vii} However, this result can be achieved by under- or over-reporting income or by adjusting actual hours worked to maximize EITC benefits, depending on circumstances, and so rules-based approaches for addressing seeming anomalies by this group may result in bias. Fortunately, there is ongoing research at the IRS to better identify misreporting of tax liabilities. Ultimately, emerging research using machine learning tools and led by IRS and academic researchers, may provide data driven insights for more accurate model-based approaches for detecting and correcting misreporting in tax data used for statistical purposes.^{viii}

It would also be helpful to have a clearer understanding of why survey respondents seem to systematically under-report some types of income, for example pension income. In work comparing IRS and Survey of Consumer Finance (SCF) estimates for components of individual income, Moore et al. found that respondents were misclassifying income components rather than intentionally or systematically underreporting total income.^{ix} This suggests that rules-based approaches to ‘correcting’ data could overstate aggregate total income in blended data. To prevent this, researchers should be developing methods to improve survey design and post-data collection processing to address these issues early in the data collection process.

4. Uses of Administrative and Survey Data in Official Statistics Must Evolve

CNSTAT and NEWS both suggest using administrative data as the frame for developing ICW data and Census has made significant progress. More broadly, large administrative data and data from commercial sources can be a cost-effective way to produce detailed sub-national estimates that are often more relevant, timely, and actionable than less granular survey-based estimates. However, both administrative and commercial data are subject to change as program requirements or industry standards evolve. For example, recent legislation changed the way tip, overtime, and some Social Security benefits are taxed. Depending on how IRS implements these changes, there may be a significant loss of income information in tax data in the future. Commercial data may also change or even disappear as businesses change ownership and evolve. Such changes in content are fairly common with administrative and commercial data. As administrative data and commercial data play a larger part in official statistics, the challenge then will be to build data systems that are resilient and stable.

To ensure that administrative data used for national statistics remain relevant will require a paradigm shift that fosters closer collaboration between the statistical system, chief data officers, and administrative program staff. Steps can be taken to preserve longitudinal stability in administrative data systems, even when program requirements change, but only if program staff understand and value these ‘downstream’ uses of program data. For example, tax data will be much more useful for ICW if IRS continues to collect data on income from tips, overtime, etc. on IRS Form 1040 even if income from these sources are exempted from tax somewhere else on the form. Having this detail will also be essential for tax compliance checks and evaluating the impacts of the new law, but it can be challenging to get program staff to consider downstream data needs when they are trying to implement legislative changes, especially when implementation timeframes are tight. A more holistic approach to data governance across government will be essential to ensure the continuity and utility of administrative data for purposes beyond immediate program management needs if these data are to play a larger role in national statistics.

Assuming data governance improves, there may be opportunities to explicitly rethink the relative roles of survey and administrative data in a 21st data infrastructure that includes integrated ICW data. In the past, agencies generally started with a carefully designed survey and then used administrative data for sampling frames, to benchmark estimates, or to reduce non-response bias. But surveys are expensive and the public’s willingness to participate has been declining for years. Costs and high nonresponse rates mean that most survey samples are not able to address the small group questions that increasingly dominate policy discussions. In

fact, CNSTAT Recommendation 3.3 is to create sub-national ICW estimates with cross tabulations by demographic characteristics. To produce these using survey data would be prohibitively costly and require major data perturbation to prevent disclosure of individual respondent data, so administrative data are likely the more practical solution.

It may then be time to think of surveys as a way to augment and improve administrative data rather than the other way round (this is actually suggested in the diagram on the right in Figure 1). Surveys might be designed specifically to benchmark administrative data and support imputation routines to correct errors or add in missing information. Giving more thought to how survey and administrative data will be blended at the time surveys are created could reduce unnecessary differences in concepts and support other steps to make the blending process easier. For example, the SCF was specifically designed to collect income data that mirrored information as reported on IRS Form 1040. This allows respondents to reference tax returns in answering these questions, improving accuracy, as well as supporting bench-marking and data cleaning.

4. Modernizing the Federal Statistical System Could Advance ICW Data

The final section of the report is devoted to data governance and recommends an expanded role for the Chief Statistician of the United States in overseeing the production of ICW data. Specifically, the report suggests creating a coordinating entity under the Chief Statistician that would do everything from codifying data sharing agreements and protocols to enabling most aspects of assembling and creating ICW, as well as overseeing the production and release of statistics produced from the data. Recommendation 5-3 implies the coordinating entity would have enforcement authority to ensure agencies adhere to report standards, etc. Fully realizing these recommendations would represent a significant expansion of the Chief Statistician's role, one which has historically been underfunded given the breadth of responsibilities already assigned under the Evidence Act. It seems unrealistic that the Chief Statistician's office would have the bandwidth to support the ICW as recommended without a significant budget and staffing boost. In addition, without clarifying legislation, the recommended oversight role would create conflicts with legal and operational environments within each agency's home department. The report also recommends creation of an external to government steering committee to coordinate the creation of and access to ICW products, something that would likely be subject to Federal Advisory Committee Act (FACA) rules. The report stops short of recommending any actual structural changes that would be needed to support these new roles. Further, OMB recently removed the career senior executive who had been the Chief Statistician since 2022, suggesting this role may be treated as a political position in future. Also recently, there has been a purge of advisory panels government-wide. Given all this, there is a need for some additional, external thinking about the future structure of a federal statistical system, including specific recommendations for legislative changes to ensure the independence of the system.

Fortunately, several non-profits have launched initiatives that could result in recommendations for modernizing the federal statistical system.^x This is an ideal opportunity to think about how some of the production, management and coordination roles associated with producing and disseminating ICW data can be built into the structure of a modernized statistical system. These efforts must also look seriously at the role of the Chief Statistician and whether that function should continue to be part of OMB or restructured in a way that would provide more independence from political influence and thus better support the ICW management functions that the CNSTAT report recommends.

Initiatives looking at the future of federal statistics must result in a specific legislative agenda to support the collaboration and data sharing needed by a modernized statistical system, and for the production of ICW data. The Foundations for Evidence-Based Policymaking Act of 2018 (Evidence Act) and other existing legislation do not permit the data sharing required to fully support an efficient, modern statistical system or create ICW.^{xi} Moreover, the statistical agencies mostly do not have authority to recommend or request legislative changes needed to improve data sharing – some of the agencies don't even have explicit authorizing statutes. Therefore, it is critical that these external to government efforts result in comprehensive recommendations for specific legislative

changes necessary to modernize the statistical system and produce ICW data. An important audience of these recommendations will be the various Congressional committees that rely on the outputs of the statistical system. These committees tend to be somewhat parochial in their thinking and will need to see how changes, especially those that allow greater data sharing across agencies, will benefit Congress' work and constituents. Only if Congressional stakeholders embrace a vision for a modernized statistical system, including integrated ICW data, will they support removing legal and structural barriers.

It is encouraging that the recently released *America's Artificial Intelligence Action Plan* assigns a significant role to a National Secure Data Service, recognizes the importance of the ICSP, and prioritizes completion of regulations to support the limited data sharing required under the Evidence Act.^{xiii} This recognition should be leveraged for modernizing the statistical system and making progress on the ICW. For example, the National Secure Data Service pilot projects include several that leverage AI to improve the utility of statistical agency data. A demonstration project that uses AI to automate at least some of the data cleaning and integration challenges associated with producing ICW data, replacing some of the manual data work that Meyer and his team have done, might be a way of both injecting new resources into the ICW data effort and reducing the overall costs.

In closing, the CNSTAT report is a good starting place for creating improved, integrated data on income, consumption, and wealth, but by assigning all the work planning and implementing the changes to a decentralized, underfunded statistical system, progress will be slow at best. This JSM session showed that academics and non-profit educational organizations can and must play a leading role in helping the agencies move the effort forward. This includes developing methodologies and demonstration products, advocating for sufficient resources and legislative changes to support data construction and shared governance, educating users and data providers, and of course producing insights using the ICW data, in partnership with agency staff when practicable, to help inform decision makers. It is encouraging that some of the needed foundational work is already underway. The researchers and non-profits that make up the statistical data ecosystem deserve much gratitude for the support they are providing federal statistics, especially during this time of great change.

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Notes

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^x See for example the American Statistical Association’s initiative <https://www.amstat.org/policy-and-advocacy/modernizing-the-federal-statistical-system>.

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^{xii} [Winning the Race: America’s AI Action Plan](#). 2025. Office of Management and Budget.